

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.19 Report from the third webinar

Public

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Coordination and Support Action (2014-2020) under grant agreement No. 101021669

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable reference number	D6.19
Deliverable name	Report from the third webinar
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Work package contributing to the deliverable	WP6
Due date	31/05/2024
Version	1.0
Actual submission date	31/07/2024

Responsible organisation	PPHS
Editor(s)	Klaudia Kaczmarek (PPHS)
Contributor(s)	-
Reviewers(s)	IANUS NPN

Disclaimer	This document reflects only the view of its authors, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.
-------------------	--

DOCUMENT CHANGE CONTROL

Version	Date	Status	Author(s), reviewer	Description
0.1	08/07/2024	Draft	Klaudia Kaczmarek (PPHS)	Initial Draft
0.2	17/07/2024 - 26/07/2024	Draft	IANUS NPN	Review by Partners
1.0	31/07/2024	Final	Klaudia Kaczmarek (PPHS)	Final review, approval and submission

Table of Contents

- 1. Summary 4
- 2. Introduction 4
- 3. 3rd CYCLOPES Webinar Series 4
 - 3.1. Main goal and program of the webinar 4
- 4. Conclusion 5

1. Summary

This document is a part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Work Package (WP6). The goal of the deliverable D6.19 “Report from the third webinar” is to report on the CYCLOPES webinar series, which were held online on 10th and 11th June 2024. These webinars are part of task 6.4. and provides an additional environment for engaging stakeholders in the cybersecurity community.

These webinar sessions are running annually and are organised in cooperation with partner networks established through WP5, in order to maximise impact and to amplify participation. The 3rd webinar series titled ‘**Solutions to Counter Child Sexual Abuse and Exploitation**’ has been organised in collaboration with other EU-funded projects and organisations working in this field.

2. Introduction

The project dissemination activities in general and the webinars in particular, are mainly construed as CYCLOPES Community networking events and focus on sharing the results among the identified and newly identified community members, stakeholders and other relevant audience of interest.

The webinars are used to complement the activities of WP2 and WP3; since the CYCLOPES workshops and Joint Live Exercises are for practitioners only, the annual webinars are ideal to reach out to a wider audience. They are used to conclude previous discussions or to launch new topic areas to be explored further. For the first webinar, the topic ‘Social Engineering aspect of Cybercrimes affecting People’ was chosen to build on the results of the 3rd CYCLOPES workshop on this topic. The subject of 2nd webinar ‘Enterprises as a Victims of Cybercrime’ has been chosen in collaboration with European Judicial Cybercrime Network (EJCN).

The CYCLOPES Community members and stakeholders’ audience are the core of the main goals of the CYCLOPES communication and dissemination activities. Throughout the duration of the project, CYCLOPES intends to build and sustain efficient community members relations in order to enable interaction between different parties and build synergies with already established networks of practitioners.

3. 3rd CYCLOPES Webinar Series

3.1. Main goal and program of the webinar

In a short series of webinars organised through the CYCLOPES network, we brought together several outstanding presentations and demonstrations from projects and private organisations working to counter child sexual abuse and exploitation (CSAE). The online sessions aim to familiarise law enforcement officers with the latest investigative tools and solutions, advancing the EU strategy’s ‘detection and investigation’ pillar to combat CSA.

The webinars started on Monday the 10th with an overview of the CYCLOPES’ practitioners’ workshop in Malta earlier in 2024. Then we had an opportunity to know the CPORT¹ project and value of Videntifier². On Tuesday the 11th we had contributions from the ARICA³, ALUNA⁴,

¹ <https://projectcport.com/>

² <https://www.videntifier.com/>

³ <https://www.aricaproject.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.aluna-isf.eu/>

and HEROES⁵ projects. We concluded with a presentation from Resolver⁶ who eloquently described the challenges posed by changes with generative AI and the proliferation of child sexual abuse materials (CSAM).

The agenda of the webinar series is presented here:

CYCLOPES

10 – 11 JUNE, 2024 WEBINAR SERIES

SOLUTIONS TO COUNTER CHILD SEXUAL ABUSE AND EXPLOITATION

MONDAY, JUNE 10TH
15:00 - 16:30 CEST

- CYCLOPES project & activities in the area of CSA
- CPORT project
- Videntifier Nexus LE

TUESDAY, JUNE 11TH
15:00 - 16:30 CEST

- ARICA project
- HEROES & ALUNA projects
- Resolver

 Funded by the European Union

Figure 1 Agenda of the 3rd webinar series

4. Conclusion

This deliverable summarises the 3rd CYCLOPES webinar series, which provided an additional opportunity to engage stakeholders within the fighting cybercrime community. During the productive sessions, participants were able to familiarise with solutions and services stemming

⁵ <https://theheroesproject.org/>

⁶ <https://www.resolver.com/>

from EU-funded projects and commercial actions focusing on combatting child sexual abuse and exploitation. The 4th CYCLOPES Webinar is planned for the first half of 2025.